

Pork Satay Menu Creation as Culinary Tourism Baha Tourism Village, Badung, Bali, Indonesia

I Nyoman Tri Sutaguna¹, I Ketut Sirna², I Gusti Bagus Rai Utama³

¹ Management Tourism of Universitas Udayana, Bali, Indonesia

^{2,3} Management Study Program of Universitas Dhyana Pura, Bali, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Analysis of the food menu offered periodically to tourists, it is hoped that the manager of the pork satay restaurant will be able to get optimal profits that can be used for business development in the future. Based on the background of the problem, the purpose of this study is to determine the process of making the types of pork satay offered by restaurant managers, and as a marketing strategy for pork satay menus in increasing food sales in the Baha tourist village area, Badung Regency, Bali. This research formulates a marketing strategy which is then elaborated with various marketing programs. Data were collected using observation, interviews, literature study, and then by using the marketing mix) namely 1) Products such as sweet pork satay, spicy pork satay; 2) Price where each menu has its price; 3) Place, namely by using direct distribution; 4) Promotion such as the installation of restaurant name signs, personal selling, sales promotion, and publicity. Then the analysis is carried out using the engineering menu. The technique of determining the informants using purposive sampling. This research will find out the menu offered by restaurant managers in the Baha tourist village area, Badung Regency, Bali, there are 4 menus (53.77%) of pork satay classified as a star, meaning that it is popular and profitable, 2 menus (46.23%) are classified as a plow horse, meaning popular but less profitable. Based on the results of the discussion, it can be suggested that restaurant managers in the Baha Tourism Village area should further improve the quality of food and beverages to get maximum profit.

KEYWORDS: Culinary Tourism, Engineering Menu, Marketing Mix, Pork Satay.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the contributors to the country's foreign exchange in improving the welfare of a region. The development of tourism will also increase other tourism supporting industries such as restaurants, accommodation places, and the rise of tourist travel agencies (Krismawintari & Utama, 2019). According to Jesslyn et al, various types of needs that tourists want are restaurant or restaurant facilities. Where this facility can provide benefits for restaurant business owners, including traditional traders who sell traditional foods (Jesslyn et al., 2016). Therefore, the restaurant manager will try to give the best so that consumers who enjoy traditional dishes can feel satisfied and will promote and loyally return at another time (Sutaguna et al., 2020a).

Baha Village, which is one of the tourist villages in Badung Regency, is starting to try to improve facilities and infrastructure to provide tourist comfort when visiting the area. Various types of restaurants are established to provide food and beverage needs to consumers to complement the facilities in the tourist village of Baha. Various facilities can be provided by restaurant managers in the tourist village of Baha to further increase interest and comfort for tourists, one of which is to provide quality food and beverages as well as excellent to tourists. Therefore, the restaurant manager in the Baha tourist village area takes steps by implementing strategies to market and evaluate food menus regularly (Sutaguna et al., 2020b).

Evaluation of the food menu, especially the pork satay menu at restaurants in the Baha tourist village area, usually emphasizes the quality of pork satay products and the standard of food prices. Food menus provided by restaurant owners will be more desirable if they always pay attention and improve according to the wishes and needs of consumers. However, it is inseparable from the expected sales targets on these food menus. The restaurant entrepreneurs of Baha Tourism Village, Badung Regency, Bali must work extra to increase consumer or tourist visits and in particular to increase sales of the types of food and beverages they have through marketing strategies to compete with other food products. Because the visits of consumers or tourists to each restaurant are not as expected, and are not maximized (Sutaguna et al., 2022).

Many consumers or tourists who come are attracted to restaurants around the Baha Tourism Village which have various kinds of food and drink offers, especially pork satay menus at more affordable prices. According to Husada et al. To win the

competition in the sale of food, the restaurant entrepreneur needs to analyze the product, namely by making the types of pork satay menus, analyzing the menu periodically to determine the marketing strategy for the pork satay menu, because often the management rarely analyzes the menu. They only rely on the history of sales, to determine the fate of this pork satay menu (Husada et al., 2018).

This step is taken to find out the condition of the menu and the wishes of the guests regarding the menu offered because a menu is also a communication tool between the restaurant and the customer so the restaurant management's ability is required to be able to promote and sell the menu offered. Periodic menu analysis is necessary to determine the level of popularity and profit level of the menu provided so that it can be used as a guide in determining the steps that must be taken to improve quality and sales in the future (Sulartiningrum & Sugiarto, 2001).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following are some descriptions of previous research that are considered relevant to this study because they discuss menu analysis in the tourism sector. According to Arcana to stimulate the development of the restaurant industry then the factors that cause the low level of tourist visits must be studied the strengths and weaknesses of internal factors and examine the opportunities and threats from external factors of restaurant industry marketing in the face of increasingly fierce competition (Arcana, 2014). Dalem formulated that the factor causing the lack of development of traditional Balinese food was the lack of effort by related parties to promote, either through the mass media or through the implementation of programs that promoted traditional Balinese food. Meanwhile, based on food analysis, which examines strengths and weaknesses as internal factors and opportunities and threats as external factors, it is known that traditional Balinese food has a very high potential to be developed. Therefore, an aggressive strategy is very likely to be applied (Dalem, 2010).

Pugra tourism development needs to involve all components, where one of the most important parts of competitive advantage in traditional Balinese food service is service by restaurant waiters. Waiters are restaurant staff whose job is to handle guest orders, bring food to restaurants and provide services to guests (Pugra, 2011). Rais stated that in designing the development of gastronomic tourism, it is possible to package the potential resources and tourism activities that are owned into a unique gastronomic tour package and can provide interesting memories for tourists. Furthermore, it is said that if you want to improve culinary quality, it is necessary to collaborate with the government as an initiator, motivator, and facilitator at the beginning of planning and development (Rais, 2011). Suardani stated that to realize the importance of restaurant survival, it is necessary to analyze the perceptions of tourists and related parties regarding food business development strategies. This can be done by utilizing information technology as an information center, promoting more vigorously, maintaining taste, and promotion needs to be improved both by using mass media and the internet (Suardani, 2017).

Based on the previous research, this research has something in common, namely, they both analyze culinary matters. The differences from previous research are the variables studied and the research locations are different.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a quantitative descriptive method that describes a series of activities that describe the results of research with analysis, description, and calculations in the form of numbers through observation, interviews, documentation, or a combination of these methods (Soehardi, 2001); (Utama dan Mahadewi, 2012).

The data collected from the results of field research uses a quantitative description approach that is compiled and expanded and in-depth in the form of numbers using engineering menu analysis techniques. Menu engineering is an evaluation tool or an evaluation method used by management or catering service managers to make the menus offered to potential customers more in line with customer tastes or interests so that the menu becomes popular and provides an adequate level of profit (Handojo, 2015).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Menu Position in Restaurants in Baha Tourism Village

Planning and preparation of menus are very important evaluation tools used by restaurant management in Baha Tourism Village. This is to make the menu offered to potential customers more in line with the tastes or interests of customers so that the menu becomes popular and provides an adequate level of profit. To determine the position of the menu, it must be based on the Ala Carte

menu which has its dishes and prices as well as sales history data. This is because the History of Sales provides an overview of the name of the food and the amount of food ordered by the customer.

Figure 1. The atmosphere of Pork Satay Restaurant Restaurant in Baha Tourism Village. Taken by Sutaguna, (2022)

4.2 Sales History.

History of Sales is a daily record of the number of portions that can be sold. This record is needed by the restaurant management in the tourist village of Baha, who can make decisions to increase sales of food and beverages (Ginting et al., 2017). The sales history alone is not enough to analyze the menus in restaurants in the tourist village of Baha. The selling price and cost of food are also very important in calculating this analysis so that maximum profit will be obtained.

4.3 Cost of Food and Selling Price of Food

According to Dewi et al. cost of food is the total cost used to make one serving of food ready to be served to guests. Before setting the selling price of food, the cost of the food needs to be calculated carefully, so that the selling price displayed is truly reliable and the profit level is flexible. Meanwhile, the selling price of food is the price charged to consumers because these costs include consideration of costs, competition, investment, types of customers, and other considerations to achieve the desired profits of the company (Dewi, 2013).

4.4 The Process of Making Various Types of Pork Satay Menu in Baha Tourism Village, Badung

Sate is a portion of authentic Indonesian food, which is also popular throughout the world. With this traditional satay food, Indonesian food, especially Bali, can become a culinary mecca at the international level. Because of the unique taste, aroma, texture, and diversity of types of satay. Many types of satay are famous in the archipelago, but satay can still be made with new creations and has a better taste (Sutaguna et al., 2020b). From the results of observations and interviews, the following are several types of pork satay found in the Baha Tourism Village restaurant, Badung Regency by using different processing methods or processes, including cooking techniques and basic ingredients for spices.

Figure 2. Menu Creations Made from Pork. Taken by Sutaguna, (2022).

Noted: All ingredient kept by authors

4.5 Recapitulation of Menu Creation Analysis

From a collection of data obtained from After this analysis, it will be followed up by making a recapitulation of the menu class results from the menu analysis at the pork satay restaurant in the tourist village of Baha in Table 1.

Table 1. Analysis of the Engineering Menu Pork Satay Menu, January – December 2021 Period

NO	A Menu Item Name	B MM	C Menu Mix %	D Food Cost (Rp)	E Selling Price (Rp)	F CM (E - D) (Rp)	G Total Cost (D x B) (Rp)	H Total Revenue (B x E) (Rp)	I Total CM (B x F) (Rp)	J CM Category	K MM Category	L Menu Category
Kategori Menu Sate Babi												
1	Sate babi bumbu kacang	2,003	23.27	5,050	11,000	5,950	10,115,150	22,033,000	11,917,850	L	H	Plow Horse
2	Sate babi sambel matah	1,976	22.96	5,400	12,000	6,600	10,670,400	23,712,000	13,041,600	L	H	Plow Horse
3	Sate babi bumbu rujak	1,005	11.68	8,200	20,000	11,800	8,241,000	20,100,000	11,859,000	H	H	Star
4	Sate babi bumbu kencur	1,551	18.02	7,150	17,000	9,850	11,089,650	26,367,000	15,277,350	H	H	Star
5	Sate babi bumbu kemiri	1,015	11.79	8,200	20,000	11,800	8,323,000	20,300,000	11,977,000	H	H	Star
6	Sate babi bumbu ketumbar	1,057	12.28	9,600	24,000	14,400	10,147,200	25,368,000	15,220,800	H	H	Star
Total		8,607					58,586,400	137,880,000	79,293,600			

Noted: Babi= Pork. Source: Data processed by researchers, 2021

4.6 Marketing Strategy at the Pork Satay Menu Restaurant in the Baha Tourism Village

From the results of the menu analysis at the restaurant in the Baha Tourism Village, it will then be summarized as follows:

- 1) Star: satay with rujak seasoning, kencur seasoning satay, candlenut satay, and coriander spiced satay
- 2) Plow horse: peanut sauce and sambal matah satay
- 3) Puzzles: none
- 4) Dog: none

Based on the menu analysis, the condition of the menu can be seen that 53.77% or 4 types of pork satay menu from the entire menu offered by restaurants in Baha Tourism Village during the January – December 2021 period are classified as Star, which means it is popular and profitable. This type of food is very popular with tourists and can provide high profits, therefore it needs to be maintained and if possible the amount is increased to increase sales volume. For that it is necessary to follow up as follows:

- 1) Maintaining the quality, quantity, and presentation of food.
- 2) Placing menu items in strategic places.
- 3) Conduct regular market reviews to find out the increase in the price of ingredients which will later be used as a reference in revising the price of the food.
- 4) Raise the price gradually as the quantity demanded increases.

Plowhorse category with a total of 2 types of food (46.23%). This type of food is popular in sales but provides low profit, it is necessary to take the following actions:

- 1) Maintaining food quality, because this type of food is favored by tourists.
- 2) Controlling the cost of goods by supervising the purchase, storage, and processing of foodstuffs.
- 3) Increasing this type of food into a star category by increasing the price gradually while still based on the development of demand.
- 4) Placing in a position that does not interfere with the start position.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

5.1 Conclusions

Based on the results of these studies, it can be concluded that the menus offered to customers need to be analyzed periodically because they will be able to get optimal benefits and can be used for business development in the future. Problems at the pork satay restaurant in the tourist village of Baha can be overcome by performing menu engineering analysis techniques to determine the level of profit, popularity, and good menu categories so that the expected targets and goals can be achieved.

To do this, it is necessary to determine the exact position of the menus at the pork satay restaurant in the Baha tourist village area. Of all the menus owned by restaurants, only the Ala Carte menu is used to determine food categories, because each type of food on this menu is separate and has its price. So that the marketing strategy used by the pork satay restaurant menu in the Baha tourist village to increase food sales are:

- 1) The Star category menu can be followed up by maintaining the quality and quantity of food, maintaining the selling price, maintaining and improving the quality of menu placement then promotion is done by providing better service to consumers.
- 2) The menu in the Plowhorse category requires supervision and control of food costs, raising prices not too much, placing a less strategic position, and then inserting the menu into special events in restaurants.
- 3) The Puzzle category menu needs to pay attention to and revise the menu to affect popularity, remove menus that have low sales, and then display menu items in strategic positions.
- 4) The Dog category menu must improve the menu by changing the name of the menu or replacing it with a new one, lowering the selling price, improving the quality of menu placement and smooth service, then placing products at low prices and vigorous promotions, for example through discounts or special offers.

5.2 Suggestions

Based on the results of the analysis that has been carried out, suggestions that can be submitted to the management of restaurants in the Baha tourist village area are:

- 1) Conduct menu analysis periodically, at least once a month. This is because menu analysis is an evaluation tool used by restaurant management in the Baha tourist village area to make the menus offered to potential customers more in line with customer tastes or interests so that the menu becomes popular and provides the maximum level of profit.
- 2) A good menu analysis is to use menu engineering analysis techniques because with this technique it will be obtained and known the level of profit, popularity, and menu categories. This is necessary to arrange the menu in the future, to obtain the expected goals.
- 3) Menus belonging to the star category, to be maintained and for the plowhorse category, to pay more attention to determining the appropriate price, to get maximum profit.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Arcana, I. N. (2014). Persepsi dan ekspektasi wisatawan mancanegara terhadap industri restoran di kabupaten badung. *Jurnal Ilmiah Hospitality Management*, 4(2), 67–92.
2. Dalem, K. P. (2010). Strategi Pengembangan Makanan Tradisional Bali pada Freestanding Restaurant Kelurahan Tanjung Benoa, Kecamatan Kuta Selatan, Kabupaten Badung-Bali (tesis). *Denpasar: Kajian Pariwisata Universitas Udayana*.
3. Dewi, M. H. U. (2013). Pengembangan desa wisata berbasis partisipasi masyarakat lokal di Desa Wisata Jatiluwih Tabanan, Bali. *Jurnal Kawistara*, 3(2).
4. Ginting, N., Rahman, N. V., & Nasution, A. D. (2017). Increasing tourism in Karo District, Indonesia based on place identity. *Environment-Behaviour Proceedings Journal*, 2(5), 177–184.
5. Handojo, S. M. (2015). Analisis Pengaruh Kualitas Makanan Dan Persepsi Harga Terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen Di D'cost Surabaya. *Jurnal Hospitality Dan Manajemen Jasa*, 3(2), 643–654.
6. Husada, D. D., Asmara, D., & Suroto, A. (2018). Pengaruh Penerapan Rekam Menu Terhadap Tingkat Penjualan di Restoran Epice Hotel Alila Solo. *Jurnal Pariwisata Indonesia*, 14(1), 94–114.
7. I Nyoman Tri Sutaguna, I., I Ketut Sirna, I., & Utama, I. (2022). Gastronomy of Pesan Tlengis as a Tourism Attraction in Werdi Bhuwana Village Bali. *I Nyoman Tri Sutaguna I Ketut Sirna I Gusti Bagus Rai Utama.(2022). Gastronomy of Pesan Tlengis as a Tourism Attraction in Werdi Bhuwana Village Bali. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 5(1), 1–6.
8. Jesslyn, M., Pricilia, C. W., & Regina, J. (2016). The Influence of Restaurant Atmosphere, Food Quality and Service Quality on Consumers' Perceived Value at De Soematra Restaurant Surabaya. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 53(9), 1689–1699.
9. Krismawintari, N. P. D., & Utama, I. G. B. R. (2019). Kajian tentang Penerapan Community Based Tourism di Daya Tarik Wisata Jatiluwih, Tabanan, Bali. *Jurnal Kajian Bali (Journal of Bali Studies)*, 9(2), 429–448.
10. Pugra, I. W. (2011). *Kepuasan Wisatawan Terhadap Pelayanan Makanan Tradisional Bali Pada Tirta Restaurant Di Sanur Beach Hotel*. tesis). Denpasar: Universitas Udayana.
11. Rais, S. (2011). *Persepsi Wisatawan Asing Terhadap Produk Hatten Wine Sebagai Seni Kuliner Bali Untuk Daya Tarik Wisata*. Doctoral Dissertation. Universitas Udayana Sadjuni. Denpasar.
12. Soehardi, S. (2001). Pengantar Metodologi Penelitian Sosial-Bisnis-Manajemen. *Yogyakarta: BPFE UST*.
13. Suardani, M. (2017). Analisis Keputusan Pengunjung Membeli Ayam Betutu pada Rumah Makan Ayam Betutu Khas Gilimanuk di Tuban Bali. *Soshum: Jurnal Sosial Dan Humaniora*, 3(2), 151.
14. Sulartiningrum, E. S., & Sugiarto, E. (2001). Pengantar Akomodasi dan restoran. *Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama*.
15. Sutaguna, I. N. T., Sirna, I. K., & Utama, I. G. B. R. (2020a). The Processing Technique of Urutan Celeng as A Superior Product for Culinary Tour in Sangeh Abiansemal Tourism Village, Badung, Bali, Indonesia. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v11i1.1460>
16. Sutaguna, I. N. T., Sirna, I. K., & Utama, I. G. B. R. (2020b). Transformation of Traditional Food with Duck Basic for Culinary Business Continuity in Ubud Tourist Village, Gianyar, Bali, Indonesia. *Technium: Romanian Journal of Applied Sciences and Technology*, 2(7). <https://doi.org/10.47577/technium.v2i7.1638>
17. Utama dan Mahadewi. (2012). Metodologi Penelitian Pariwisata dan Perhotelan, Edisi 1. Yogyakarta: ANDI. *AndiPublisher*, 82. <http://andipublisher.com/produk-0113004600-metodologi-penelitian-pariwisata-dan-per.html>

Cite this Article: I Nyoman Tri Sutaguna, I Ketut Sirna, I Gusti Bagus Rai Utama (2022). Pork Satay Menu Creation as Culinary Tourism Baha Tourism Village, Badung, Bali, Indonesia. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 5(4), 1312-1317